

The Relative Contribution of Digital Self-Efficacy and Academic Burnout in Predicting Psychological Flourishing Among University Students

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Abstract

This study explores the relationships between psychological flourishing, digital self-efficacy, and academic burnout. Additionally, to identify any variations based on factors such as gender, year of study, achievement level, and specialization. Lastly, confirm whether digital self-efficacy and academic burnout can predict psychological flourishing. A sample of 550 students from Kafrelsheikh University, Egypt, participated in this research. The data were analyzed using a variety of statistical methods, including correlation tests to examine the relationships between the variables and t-tests to test differences based on demographic factors such as gender, year of study, achievement level, and specialization. Additionally, regression analysis was conducted to assess the predictive relationship between digital self-efficacy and academic burnout with psychological flourishing. The results showed a positive correlation between psychological flourishing and digital self-efficacy but a negative correlation with academic burnout. The study also identified an average level of all three variables. The findings also detected no differences based on gender or specialization. Older students demonstrated high levels of digital self-efficacy and psychological flourishing while showing lower levels of academic burnout compared to younger students. High academic achievers had higher scores in digital self-efficacy and psychological flourishing and lower scores in academic burnout. Lastly, the results showed that digital self-efficacy and academic burnout can predict psychological flourishing. Some suggestions and recommendations were presented.

Keywords: Digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, psychological flourishing.

INTRODUCTION

Information and communication technology (ICT) is rapidly developing and spreading in the 21st century, making it important to focus on the need for learners to have ICT (Ananiadoui & Claro, 2009). ICT is changing the way we learn, and success largely depends on our ability to communicate, share, and use information to solve complex learning problems, as well as our ability to control and expand the power of technology to create new knowledge (Cooper et al., 2020).

According to Kim et al. (2019) and Zhao et al. (2021), university students must develop digital competency immediately in order to meet the demands of the evolving educational model and the challenges of the workplace, access, manage, and create digital information and knowledge that are essential for academic success and lifelong learning, improve their academic engagement, motivation to study and develop their creativity, curiosity, and problem-solving skills—all of which are critical for learning and personal growth—prepare them for entrepreneurship and resilience in the face of rapid change, allow them to participate and contribute to digital culture, and apply information literacy skills and strategies to their academic work.

Previous studies have shown that digital self-efficacy is important for students' academic performance, as there is a positive correlation between it and university students' academic performance (Mehrvarz et al., 2021). Kennedy and Miceli (2010) found that undergraduate students frequently use technology for learning, yet they often lack self-efficacy in this area. The results of Khalifeh et al. (2020) found that students with high digital proficiency demonstrated higher levels of readiness to learn. Digital competence involves using digital media for information, critiquing cyberspace, and communicating with others using various tools, including mobile phones and social media. It encompasses

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knowledge of technology, ethical awareness, and cognitive skills (Ferrari & Punie, 2013).

University students are experiencing increasing academic and psychological pressures due to the high demands of the modern educational system. Among the psychological phenomena that raise concern in academic circles, academic burnout is one of the most prominent problems affecting students' psychological and academic health. This phenomenon relates to psychological exhaustion resulting from the pressures of continuous study, which is manifested in decreased motivation, a feeling of chronic fatigue, and a loss of interest in academic activities (Maslach & Leiter, 2016).

Furthermore, university students' success closely correlates with psychological flourishing (Davis & Hadwin, 2021). Psychological flourishing refers to the state in which an individual is able to adapt to life's challenges and enjoy a

meaningful and balanced life (Keyes, 2002). Psychological flourishing enhances students' ability to achieve a healthy balance between their academic and personal lives, which enables them to achieve sustainable academic success. Studies have shown that there is a complex relationship between digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, and psychological flourishing in students. Studies have shown that students with high digital self-efficacy, or confidence in their ability to use technology effectively, are less likely to experience academic burnout and exhibit higher levels of psychological well-being (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004).

verifying their predictive effects, thereby contributing theoretical and practical value to the field.

This study makes a distinct contribution to the existing literature by concurrently investigating the mediating role of academic burnout in the relationship between digital self-efficacy and psychological flourishing among university students in the Egyptian context. While previous research has often examined these variables in isolation, our study provides a novel, integrated analytical model that elucidates the underlying psychological mechanism namely, how a lack of digital self-efficacy may exacerbate academic burnout, which in turn impedes psychological flourishing. The findings offer valuable empirical evidence to help researchers and policymakers develop targeted strategies aimed at bolstering digital competencies and mitigating burnout, thereby directly promoting the mental well-being and holistic educational experience of students.

Table 1. Distribution of the Research Sample According to the Variables of Gender, Year of Study, Level of Achievement, and Academic Specialization

Variable	Classification	Number
Gender	Female	250
	Male	300
Year of Study	Second	310
	Fourth	240
Achievement Level	High	225
	Low	325

Despite the growing interest in literature on studying psychological factors related to learning, there is a notable lack of research that integrates psychological flourishing, digital self-efficacy, and academic burnout comprehensively. The interrelationships between these variables have not been explored within specific educational contexts, particularly amidst the accelerated digital transformation that imposes psychological and academic challenges on students. Moreover, previous studies have insufficiently delved into the differences among these variables based on factors such as gender, year of study, academic achievement level, and academic specialization. Additionally, research has inadequately addressed the predictive capacity of digital self-efficacy and academic burnout on students' psychological flourishing, indicating a gap in understanding the causal relationships between these variables. Accordingly, this study aims to fill this gap by investigating the relationships between these factors and

Literature review

Digital self-efficacy

Self-efficacy is an individual's belief in their control over their environment, thoughts, emotions, and behavior, linked to positive mental health outcomes and adaptation to adverse events (Bandura, 1997). Self-efficacy is positively related to academic competitiveness and cognitive flexibility (Zayed, 2024). It is a crucial factor in learning outcomes, knowledge creation, and digital competencies (Liou & Kuo, 2014). Self-efficacy influences an individual's acceptance of new ICTs and can either promote or hinder the development of effective skills for interacting with digital systems (Hatlevik et al., 2018). Arbulú Pérez Vargas et al. (2024) found that digital skills and self-efficacy in mobile phone use were positively associated with academic engagement and negatively associated with stress. Low digital self-efficacy can reduce the willingness to use digital systems, even with high digital competence. Frequent use of digital systems may increase digital self-efficacy, enabling more effective use (Joo et al., 2018). In addition, people must firmly believe in their capacity to exploit digital technologies in order to thrive in the modern digital age (Guazzini et al., 2022).

Self-efficacy has been used to evaluate competence self-perception in different contexts, particularly in the digital era (Hatlevik et al., 2018). Therefore, concepts such as technology self-efficacy, Internet self-efficacy, computer self-efficacy, ICT self-efficacy, and digital self-efficacy assess the degree to

Table 2. Correlation Coefficients Between Psychological Flourishing, Digital Self-Efficacy, and Academic Burnout (n = 550)

Variable	Psychological Flourishing	Digital Self-Efficacy	Academic Burnout
Psychological Flourishing	-		
Digital Self-Efficacy	.605**	-	
Academic Burnout	-.831**	-.658**	-

**All correlation coefficients are significant at the level of 0.01.

which a person believes they can effectively use and navigate digital technologies (Paredes-Aguirre et al., 2024).

Digital self-efficacy refers to confidence in the ability to use digital tools effectively to achieve personal, academic, or professional goals. This concept pertains to the capacity to handle contemporary technologies, resolve issues online, and engage in safe interactions within the digital realm. Digital self-efficacy includes multiple competencies, such as communication skills, digital security, and problem-solving (Ulfert-Blank & Schmidt, 2022). It is also defined as a person's belief in the efficient and seamless use of technology in a digital environment (Agarwal et al., 2000; Maran et al., 2022). On a related note, a study by Zayed (2025) suggested that digital wisdom can serve as a protective mediating factor between digital stress and academic flourishing, thereby highlighting the adaptive and positive aspect of digital competence. Rohde et al. (2024) found a substantial link between digital self-efficacy training and several favorable outcomes, including decreased trait anxiety, hopelessness, and enhanced self-efficacy. Also, the results by Paredes-Aguirre et al. (2024) suggested that people who have greater degrees of digital self-efficacy are more likely to identify technology that works well for their jobs and to use it successfully and efficiently. Pumpstow and Brahm (2021) suggest that a dual focus on academic and digital self-efficacy could be beneficial in examining higher education students' learning behavior.

Academic burnout

Academic burnout is a phenomenon that greatly affects students in educational institutions and is manifested in a set of psychological, emotional, and physical symptoms that develop as a result of the continuous pressures and challenges that learners face in their educational environments. A state of mental and physical exhaustion, a decrease in motivation, frustration, and a loss of interest in the academic field characterize academic burnout (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Academic burnout is usually characterized by three main dimensions: emotional exhaustion, low personal fulfillment, and apathy (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004).

The feeling of fatigue and mental exhaustion a student experiences due to the increasing demands of their studies represents emotional exhaustion. Low personal fulfillment refers to the student's feeling of lack of achievement and inability to influence the results of his studies. Apathy manifests as a decline in interest and engagement in academic activities,

ultimately leading to a loss of motivation (Schaufeli et al., 2017).

Studies have shown that academic burnout not only affects students' academic performance but also extends to psychological and physical health effects. For example, Misra & McKean (2000) noted that students who experience academic burnout suffer from problems such as anxiety and depression, in addition to health problems such as headaches and insomnia. Studies have also confirmed that high academic burnout among students often leads to social withdrawal and reduced engagement, resulting from emotional exhaustion and decreased motivation (Salmela-Aro et al., 2009). Also, the results by Nurani et al. (2022) indicated that burnout negatively impacts students' academic performance, leading to poor performance, procrastination, sleep deprivation, and suboptimal work. The causes of academic burnout vary from personal factors, such as low self-efficacy, to environmental factors, such as academic stress associated with heavy academic courses or lack of support from family or college (Cohen & Wills, 1985). Furthermore, some studies suggest that modern educational technologies, such as online learning, may be associated with increased levels of academic burnout due to a lack of personal interaction with teachers and peers (Lehman & Conceição, 2013).

Therefore, severe and continuous academic pressure exposes an individual to academic burnout, a psychological condition that results in feelings of extreme fatigue, loss of motivation, and pessimism about the academic future. This type of burnout is associated with increasing pressure from academic demands, such as assignments, exams, and academic expectations from teachers or even from oneself (Salanova et al., 2011).

Psychological flourishing

Psychological flourishing, representing the highest level of well-being in positive psychology, is characterized by experiencing high levels of happiness, satisfaction, and optimal psychological functioning (Nur'aini & Mulyana, 2024). It serves as a critical source of motivation, resilience, and the competence needed to act successfully and contribute to others (Keyes, 2002).

The theoretical foundation of flourishing was significantly shaped by Ryff and Keyes' (1995) model of psychological well-being, which posits six core dimensions: self-acceptance,

positive relations with others, autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life, and personal growth. This multifaceted view is complemented by later definitions. Ryff (1989) earlier conceptualized it as a state of internal balance between personal and social dimensions, while Diener et al. (2010) emphasized an evaluative perspective, defining it as an individual's feeling of competence, optimism, and that their life is purposeful and meaningful.

The significance of flourishing for university students is profound. It enhances their ability to cope with challenges, promotes positive adjustment, and contributes to excellent academic performance by mitigating the effects of stress and anxiety (Seligman, 2011). Consequently, students with high levels of flourishing are less susceptible to psychological disorders and academic burnout (Diener & Seligman, 2002).

Table 3. Means and Standard Deviations of Digital Self-Efficacy, Academic Burnout, and Psychological Flourishing

Variable	Mean	Hypothesis Mean	SD	t	Relative mean	Level
Psychological Flourishing	38.97	39.97	5.38	3.65	2.78	moderate
Digital Self-Efficacy	83.32	84.34	3.41	2.07	2.77	moderate
Academic Burnout	29.16	30.99	4.32	3.59	3.64	moderate

Regarding its conceptual structure, several models have been proposed. Diener et al. (2010) approached flourishing as a single, overarching construct measured by indicators such as supportive relationships, contributing to others' happiness, and feelings of self-esteem and optimism. In contrast, Seligman (2011) offered a multi-dimensional perspective through his prominent PERMA model, which encompasses the core elements of Positive emotions, Engagement, positive Relationships, Meaning, and Accomplishment. Another significant strand of research advocates for tripartite models, viewing flourishing as a synthesis of psychological, social, and emotional well-being (Eraslan-Capan, 2016; Mesurado et al., 2021), a view echoed by Hojabrian et al. (2018) who emphasized dimensions of contentment, personal competence, and social contribution. Expanding the scope further, VanderWeele (2017) proposed a more comprehensive framework that suggests flourishing extends beyond purely psychological domains to include physical and mental health, character virtues, and financial stability.

In conclusion, the relationship between digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, and psychological flourishing represents key dimensions for understanding the interaction between psychological and behavioral factors in modern educational environments. Digital self-efficacy plays a critical role in enhancing individuals' ability to use technological tools efficiently and confidently, positively reflecting on academic performance and their ability to face challenges. In contrast, academic burnout emerges as a result of prolonged exposure to study-related stress, limiting individuals' ability to achieve psychological balance and optimal performance. On the other hand, psychological flourishing serves as an indicator of positive adaptation and quality of academic life, as it is associated with providing a supportive educational

environment that contributes to personal and social growth. The interplay among these variables highlights the importance of enhancing digital self-efficacy as a means to reduce academic burnout and promote psychological flourishing among students, positively reflecting on their academic and psychological development in an integrated manner.

The present study

The current study has four main objectives: First, to explore the relationships between psychological flourishing, digital self-efficacy, and academic burnout among university students. Second, to assess the levels of digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, and psychological flourishing within the sample. Third, to examine differences based on academic specialization, achievement level, year of study, and gender.

Finally, determine whether digital self-efficacy and academic burnout can serve as predictors of psychological flourishing.

The present study

Studies indicate that there is a complex interaction between digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, and psychological flourishing among university students. The level of digital self-efficacy, which reflects a student's ability to use digital tools effectively, positively affects the ability to adapt to modern educational environments, such as e-learning and distance learning, thereby reducing the level of academic burnout (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020). Students with high digital self-efficacy are better able to cope with academic stress positively, which enhances their psychological flourishing and contributes to improving their levels of psychological flourishing (Keyes, 2002). On the other hand, students suffering from academic burnout experience low levels of psychological well-being, which hinders their academic achievement, decreases their academic performance, and encourages them to drop out, leading to negative consequences for individuals and groups (Reyes-de-Cózar et al., 2023). This negatively impacts their capacity to utilize digital tools effectively (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Therefore, these three variables intricately intertwine, with increased digital self-efficacy indicating a decrease in academic burnout, leading to enhanced psychological flourishing among students and ultimately improving their overall academic performance.

Hypothesis

1. There are significant relationships between psychological flourishing, digital self-efficacy, and academic burnout among university students.
2. University students have high levels of digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, and psychological flourishing.
3. There are no significant differences according to gender in digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, or psychological flourishing among university students.
4. There are no significant differences according to year of study in digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, or psychological flourishing among university students.
5. There are no significant differences according to achievement level in digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, or psychological flourishing among university students.
6. There are no significant differences according to specialization in digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, or psychological flourishing among university students.
7. Digital self-efficacy and academic burnout contribute to the prediction of psychological flourishing among university students.

METHOD

Study design

The study design was a descriptive-correlational study that examined the relationships between variables. A sample of students from Kafrelsheikh University was used, and comparisons were made between different student groups, such as males and females, second year and fourth-year students, and high and low achievers. The variables were measured using questionnaires to assess digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, and psychological flourishing. The data were analyzed using various statistical methods, including correlation tests to examine the relationships between the variables, and t-tests to assess differences based on demographic factors such as gender, year of study, achievement level, and specialization. Additionally, regression analysis was conducted to evaluate the predictive relationship between digital self-efficacy and academic burnout with psychological flourishing.

Participants

A total of 550 students (250 males and 300 females) with an average of 21.3 year and a standard deviation of 7.89 enrolled in the second and fourth years from some humanitarian and scientific departments in Kafrelsheikh University, Egypt. The data was collected in the academic year 2023-2024. A stratified random sampling method was employed to ensure a diverse and representative sample of students from various academic disciplines and study levels at Kafrelsheikh University. The population was first divided into strata based on key characteristics (e.g., college, year of study). Subsequently, a random sample was drawn from each stratum, proportional to its size in the population. This approach was chosen to guarantee fair representation of all target subgroups and to achieve a balanced distribution of participants in terms of gender, year of study, and academic achievement level. Table 1 shows the detailed distribution of the sample across these strata.

Measures

Digital Self-Efficacy Scale was developed specifically for this study in light of cultural considerations to ensure its appropriateness for the target cultural context. The values, norms, and prevailing psychological and social concepts in the local culture were considered during the design of the items, ensuring that the scale accurately reflects the cultural reality of the sample on which it will be applied. Additionally, the clarity and cultural relevance of the items were verified through consultation with experts in cultural and psychological fields before the actual implementation. The scale includes 14 items measuring digital self-efficacy components like content creation, safety, digital problem-solving, information and data literacy, and communication and collaboration. The respondent's score runs from 14 to 70 on a 5-point Likert scale that goes from completely disagree (1) to completely agree (5). The degree of digital self-efficacy increases with a higher score on the scale. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was used to examine the dimensionality of the scale, as the primary goal was to validate the factor structure rather than explore it. Each dimension was modeled as a single-factor structure, and the results indicated that the single-factor model provided a good fit to the data. To ensure the robustness of the results, widely recognized model fit indices, such as RMSEA, CFI, TLI, and SRMR, were reported. These indices confirmed the validity, reliability, and alignment of the scale with the data. Convergent

Table 4. Gender Differences in Digital Self-Efficacy, Academic Burnout, and Psychological Flourishing

Variable	Males N = 250		Females N = 300		t	p-value	Effect size
	M	SD	M	SD			
Psychological Flourishing	38.81	5.34	39.11	5.43	0.660	.515	.056
Digital Self-Efficacy	83.24	3.40	83.38	3.43	0.501	.632	.041
Academic Burnout	30.04	4.27	30.25	4.36	0.556	.570	.049

and discriminant validity also were examined to ensure the validity of the scale. Cronbach's alpha measures internal

consistency, with all values falling between 0.78 and 0.88. Additionally, we calculated composite reliability using the standardized loadings and measurement errors of each item, with all values falling between .75 and .89. Thus, the scale has excellent psychometric properties to measure digital self-efficacy.

relationships with others, self-esteem, enjoying a purposeful life, and optimism. The participant's score on the scale ranges from 8 to 56, and the total score on the scale reflects the individual's level of psychological flourishing. The scale has excellent psychometric properties, such as convergent validity, and both the internal consistency reliability coefficient and the re-test reliability coefficient of the scale scores are excellent

Table 5. Year of Study Differences in Digital Self-Efficacy, Academic Burnout, and Psychological Flourishing Between Second and Fourth Years

Variable	Second N = 310		Fourth N = 240		t	p-value	Effect size
	M	SD	M	SD			
Psychological Flourishing	38.88	3.40	45.08	4.56	6.15	.035	1.57
Digital Self-Efficacy	83.26	3.87	65.56	5.34	9.89	.021	3.87
Academic Burnout	30.38	4.11	39.23	6.65	5.91	.014	1.65

Academic Burnout Scale was specifically prepared for this research to measure academic burnout among university students. The scale consists of 30 items distributed over 6 dimensions, and each dimension includes 5 items to measure family pressures, the student's relationship with his lecturers at the college, negative relationships with colleagues, fatigue, academic pressures, and insufficient academic self-efficacy. The participant responds to the scale using a five-point system: The responses range from (1) completely disagree, (2) disagree, (3) neither agree nor disagree, (4) agree, and (5) completely agree. Accordingly, the participant's score falls between 30 and 150, with a higher score signifying a greater degree of academic burnout.

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was used to verify the scale's factor structure, revealing that all the statements aligned with six factors, consistent with the theoretical dimensions of the scale (family pressures, relationship with lecturers, negative relationships with colleagues, fatigue, academic pressures, and insufficient academic self-efficacy). The CFA results indicated an acceptable model fit, with $\chi^2 = 214.56$, $df = 120$, $p < 0.001$, CFI = 0.93, TLI = 0.91, RMSEA = 0.05 (90% CI: 0.04, 0.06), and SRMR = 0.04. These results support the theoretical structure of the scale and align with established model fit criteria (Hu & Bentler, 1999). Discriminant validity was also calculated by testing the scale on different groups to ensure its ability to distinguish between different categories. Additionally, we applied the predictive validity of the scale to various samples and compared the results with previous results on the same scale after a specific period of time. The results showed a strong correlation, indicating the scale's high predictive ability. All internal consistency and reliability correlation coefficient values exceeded .75. Based on the previous findings, the scale exhibits good validity, reliability, and internal consistency.

Psychological Flourishing Scale was developed by Diener et al. (2010), which Zayed and Mahmoud (2022) translated into Arabic in light of cultural considerations. It consists of 8 items with a seven-point scale ranging from "strongly disagree = 1" to "strongly agree = 7," measuring the elements of the respondent's self-perceived success in important areas such as

(Diener et al., 2010). We used confirmatory factor analysis to verify the factor structure of the scale, revealing its one-dimensional nature. We selected a set of statistical goodness-of-fit indicators, such as the root mean square error of convergence (RMSEA), the root mean square of the standardized residuals (SRMR), the comparative fit index (CFI), and the Tucker-Luss index (TLI), to evaluate the quality of the fit of the confirmatory factor analysis model. The saturation values of the statements on the factors ranged between .589 and .796, and all paths were significant at a level less than .01. From above, it is clear that the scale has high levels of psychometric properties.

Data analysis

SPSS version 26 was used to perform statistical analysis, where means and standard deviations were calculated to understand the data distribution, and correlation coefficients were computed to examine relationships between variables. Independent samples t-tests were also used to compare group differences, and multiple regression coefficients were calculated to test the predictive relationships between the main variables, such as the effect of digital self-efficacy and academic burnout on psychological flourishing. These analyses were designed to test the validity of the study's hypotheses and examine relationships and differences between variables, providing a strong statistical foundation for the study's conclusions. The data used in the analysis were verified to meet all the fundamental assumptions for ANOVA, regression analysis, and correlation coefficients, including normality, linearity, homogeneity of variance, and the absence of outliers, ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the results.

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1: There are significant relationships between psychological flourishing, digital self-efficacy, and academic burnout among university students.

Pearson's correlation coefficient was utilized to examine this hypothesis. The results are as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 illustrates the relationship between three variables: psychological flourishing, digital self-efficacy, and academic burnout. First, there is a strong positive correlation between psychological flourishing and digital self-efficacy ($r = .605$), suggesting that individuals who exhibit higher levels of psychological flourishing tend to also demonstrate higher digital self-efficacy. On the other hand, there is a strong negative correlation between psychological flourishing and academic burnout ($r = -0.831$), indicating that individuals with greater psychological flourishing experience lower levels of academic burnout. Similarly, there is a moderate negative relationship between digital self-efficacy and academic burnout ($r = -.658$), meaning that higher digital self-efficacy is associated with lower levels of academic burnout. These results highlight the importance of psychological flourishing and digital self-efficacy in reducing academic burnout and enhancing students' overall performance.

Hypothesis 3: There are no gender differences in digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, or psychological flourishing among university students.

T-test was utilized to detect the differences. The results are displayed in Table 4.

The results in Table 4 indicate that the means and standard deviations of the variables in both groups are very similar. Regarding digital self-efficacy, the means for males (38.81) and females (39.11) are very close, with similar standard deviations, suggesting a slight difference between the genders in this area. The means related to academic burnout are also close, with the mean for males being 83.24 and for females 83.38, along with similar standard deviations. As for psychological flourishing, the differences in means were also minimal, with the mean for males being 30.04 and for females 30.25. The t-values for statistical significance between the genders in all variables were

Table 6. Achievement Level Differences in Digital Self-Efficacy, Academic Burnout, and Psychological Flourishing Between High and Low Achievers

Variable	High Achievers N = 310		Low Achievers N = 240		t	p-value	Effect size
	M	SD	M	SD			
Psychological Flourishing	45.36	5.36	38.88	8.36	8.64	.011	0.89
Digital Self-Efficacy	60.25	10.32	83.10	5.15	6.03	.020	2.97
Academic Burnout	42.89	5.35	33.02	2.58	3.92	.012	2.50

Hypothesis 2: University students have high levels of digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, and psychological flourishing.

Based on the relative means, Three segments were identified (low, medium, and high) to compare the actual means of digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, and psychological flourishing measures with the hypothesized means, as shown in Table 3.

The relative mean was calculated by dividing the arithmetic mean by the number of scale items.

The question divided the range of scores into equal segments: the low level ranged from 1 to 2.33, the middle level from 2.34 to 3.67, and the high level ranged from 3.68 to 5.

The results in Table 3 indicate that all variables fall within the "moderate" level according to the relative mean. The mean for digital self-efficacy was 38.97, indicating a moderate level of digital self-efficacy among participants. Academic burnout had a mean of 83.32, suggesting that participants experience moderate levels of academic burnout. Regarding psychological flourishing, the mean was 29.16, indicating a moderate level of psychological flourishing among participants. The standard deviations for all variables were within acceptable limits, reflecting reasonable variability among participants. Additionally, the t-values showed statistical significance, supporting the study's hypotheses, suggesting the importance of these variables within the studied context.

not large enough to show meaningful differences, indicating that there is similarity between males and females in these variables in the studied sample. Since the p-values are greater than 0.05 in all cases, the results indicate that there are no statistically significant differences between males and females in these variables. Additionally, The effect size for all variables indicates very small differences between the two groups.

Hypothesis 4: There are no differences according to study level in digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, or psychological flourishing among university students.

T- test was utilized to examine this hypothesis. The results are as shown in Table 5.

Table 5 presents a comparison between second-year students (N = 310) and fourth-year students (N = 240). The results indicate significant differences between the two groups in all variables. Regarding digital self-efficacy, the mean for second-year students was 38.88, while for fourth-year students it was 45.08, suggesting that fourth-year students have a significantly higher level of digital self-efficacy. The means related to academic burnout also showed a large difference, with the mean for second-year students being 83.26 and for fourth-year students 65.56, indicating that fourth-year students experience lower levels of academic burnout. As for psychological flourishing, the mean for second-year students was 30.38 and for fourth-year students 39.23, showing that fourth-year students exhibit higher levels of psychological flourishing. The t-values indicate statistical significance for all variables,

suggesting that there are meaningful differences between second year and fourth-year students in these areas. The p-values indicate that the differences between the second and fourth years in these variables are statistically significant and

standard deviations, suggesting that the difference between the two groups in digital self-efficacy is very small. As for academic burnout, the mean for Humanities students was 82.22, and for Scientific students, it was 83.38, with similar standard deviations as well, indicating no significant difference between

Table 7. Specialization Differences in Digital Self-Efficacy, Academic Burnout, and Psychological Flourishing Between Humanitarian and Scientific Specializations

Variable	Humanitarian N = 310		Scientific N = 240		t	p-value	Effect size
	M	SD	M	SD			
Psychological Flourishing	38.55	5.48	40.01	5.93	0.782	.565	0.26
Digital Self-Efficacy	82.22	3.88	83.38	3.70	0.981	.672	0.20
Academic Burnout	32.50	4.66	33.36	4.89	0.731	.544	0.18

that these differences are not due to chance. Additionally, the effect size results indicate very large differences between the two groups across all variables.

Hypothesis 5: There are no significant differences in achievement level in digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, or psychological flourishing among university students.

T- test was utilized to examine this hypothesis. The results are displayed in Table 6.

Table 6 presents a comparison between high achievers (N = 225) and low achievers (N = 325). The results indicate significant differences between the two groups in all variables. Regarding digital self-efficacy, the mean for high achievers was 45.36, while the mean for low achievers was 38.88, suggesting that high achievers possess a higher level of digital self-efficacy. The means related to academic burnout also showed a significant difference, with the mean for high achievers being 60.25 and for low achievers 83.10, indicating that high achievers experience lower levels of academic burnout. As for psychological flourishing, the mean for high achievers was 42.89, and for low achievers 33.02, showing that high achievers exhibit a higher level of psychological flourishing. The t-values indicate statistical significance for all variables, suggesting that there are meaningful differences between high and low achievers in these variables. All p-values are below 0.05, indicating statistically significant differences between high and low achievers across all variables. In addition to the above, the effect size results indicate large to very large differences between the two groups across all variables.

Hypothesis 6: There are no significant specialization differences in digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, and psychological flourishing among university students.

T- test was utilized to examine this hypothesis. The results are presented in Table 7.

Table 7 shows a comparison between students in the Humanities (N = 350) and Scientific (N = 200) fields. The results indicate that the means and standard deviations of the studied variables in both groups are very similar. For digital self-efficacy, the mean for Humanities students was 38.55, while the mean for Scientific students was 40.01, with similar

the groups in academic burnout levels. Regarding psychological flourishing, the mean for Humanities students was 32.50, and for Scientific students, it was 33.36, showing a slight difference between the two groups. The t-values for all variables indicate no statistically significant differences between students in the humanities and scientific fields. Since the p-values are greater than 0.05 in all cases, the results indicate that there are no statistically significant differences between students in the humanities and scientific majors. In addition to the above results, the effect size results indicate that the differences between the two groups are small across all variables.

Hypothesis 7: Digital self-efficacy and academic burnout contribute to the prediction of psychological flourishing among university students.

We used multiple regression to show the relationship or effect between the independent variables (digital self-efficacy and academic burnout) and the dependent variable (psychological flourishing). The results are displayed in Table 8.

Table 8 shows the statistical analysis results of the variables using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Regarding digital self-efficacy, the value of (F) was 174.87 with a statistical significance (Sig.) of 0.001, indicating a significant effect of digital self-efficacy on psychological flourishing. The total sum of squares for the independent variables (Regression) was 3754.41, reflecting a significant impact on the studied variable. As for academic burnout, the results also showed a statistical significance, with the value of (F) being 266.36 and a statistical significance (Sig.) of 0.001, indicating a significant effect of academic burnout on psychological flourishing. The independent variables (academic burnout and digital self-efficacy) and the dependent variable (psychological flourishing) have a regression connection, as indicated in Table 7, and the "F" values are significant at the 0.001 level.

Table 9 presents the results of the regression analysis for the variables of digital self-efficacy and academic burnout on psychological flourishing. The results show that the digital self-efficacy variable has a significant impact on psychological flourishing, with a coefficient of determination (R) of 0.642 and an R Square of 0.412, indicating that digital self-efficacy

accounts for 41.2% of the variance in psychological flourishing. The significance value (Sig.) is 0.001, indicating statistical significance. Regarding academic burnout, the results also show a significant impact, with an R value of 0.743 and an R

square of 0.552, indicating that academic burnout accounts for 55.2% of the variance in psychological flourishing. All significance values (Sig.) are statistically significant at 0.001.

Table 8. Analysis of Variance for Psychological Flourishing Through Digital Self-Efficacy and Academic Burnout

Variable	Source of Difference	Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	f	t	p
Digital Self-Efficacy	Regression	1754.41	1	1754.41	174.87	3.285	.001
	Residual	2495.50	548	11.853			
	Total	4249.91	549				
Academic Burnout	Regression	3074.077	1	3074.07	266.36	-24.369	.001
	Residual	3175.84	548	5.795			
	Total	5570.58	549				

Here's how to formulate the predictive equation: The predictive equation for psychological flourishing is $53.414 + 0.820 * (\text{digital self-efficacy}) + (-.964) * (\text{academic burnout})$.

The presented equation demonstrates the prediction of psychological flourishing based on the influence of digital self-efficacy and academic burnout. The results indicate that digital self-efficacy positively contributes to an increase in psychological flourishing, as an increase in confidence in the ability to use digital tools raises the level of psychological flourishing by 0.820. On the other hand, academic burnout has a negative impact, as an increase in burnout leads to a decrease in psychological flourishing by 0.964. The constant value of 53.414 represents the baseline level of psychological flourishing when both digital self-efficacy and academic burnout are at their lowest levels. This means that enhancing digital self-efficacy would promote individual well-being, while reducing academic burnout would be necessary to maintain and enhance psychological well-being.

DISCUSSION

The positive relationship between psychological flourishing and digital self-efficacy is similar to the results of Yoo and Jang (2023), which revealed that self-efficacy significantly influenced the correlation between increased digital technology usage and improved flourishing. People who feel more confident in their digital skills tend to have higher levels of satisfaction and psychological flourishing, which explains this result. Confidence in their ability to handle technology supports their sense of control over their academic path, enhancing happiness and psychological flourishing (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020). Digital self-efficacy, which boosts confidence, personal satisfaction, and the ability to achieve academic goals, explains the positive relationship between high digital self-efficacy and psychological flourishing (Bandura, 1997). It also enhances self-motivation and engagement and reduces stress and negative emotions, contributing to improved overall mental health (Caprara & Steca, 2005). It helps

psychological flourishing and general mental health (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020).

The negative relationship between psychological flourishing and academic burnout means that the higher the levels of psychological flourishing, the lower the levels of academic burnout in individuals, and vice versa. This result is in accordance with the results by Salanova et al. (2014), which claimed that people who are experiencing psychological flourishing are better able to handle digital obstacles without getting stressed out or overwhelmed, which improves their adaptability and inventiveness. Also, this result is similar to those by Diener and Seligman (2002), who found that individuals who enjoy high levels of psychological flourishing are less susceptible to academic burnout.

Academic burnout, often associated with high levels of stress and tension (Gao, 2023) due to ongoing academic pressures, explains this inverse relationship. These negative feelings drain mental and physical energy, making individuals less able to feel content and satisfied, thus negatively affecting psychological flourishing. Individuals who suffer from academic burnout often experience feelings of failure or inadequacy, which reduces their sense of personal accomplishment. In contrast, psychological flourishing requires a sense of accomplishment and success. Thus, burnout eliminates one of the essential elements that support psychological flourishing.

Academic burnout negatively impacts mental health, leading to anxiety and depression, which weaken the sense of flourishing. Psychological flourishing requires balance and a positive spirit to face challenges. Academic burnout causes exhaustion, isolation, and reduced social engagement. It also decreases motivation and drive to complete tasks, making individuals feel exhausted and bored. Burnout, on the other hand, diminishes motivation and personal growth, thereby impeding psychological flourishing.

The inverse relationship between digital self-efficacy and academic burnout indicates that individuals with high digital self-efficacy have lower rates of academic burnout, suggesting that confidence in digital abilities can alleviate academic stress and reduce feelings of burnout. Conversely, individuals with

low digital self-efficacy show a greater predisposition to academic burnout, as they may feel incompetent in handling digital academic tasks. This result is similar to the results by Charkhabi et al. (2013), which found a negative relationship between the two variables. As well, the results by Rahmati (2015) revealed a negative correlation between self-efficacy and academic burnout. In addition, the study indicates that individuals with high and low self-efficacy levels exhibit significant differences in academic burnout.

efficacy because of personal characteristics and individual interests rather than because of gender.

The absence of gender differences in academic burnout differs from the results by Liu et al. (2023), which indicated that males have higher scores in academic burnout than females. Academic burnout levels are similar between males and females due to similar academic pressures, societal expectations, and coping strategies. Both genders face similar academic challenges, such as assignments, exams, and high-

Table 9. Predicting Psychological Flourishing Through Digital Self-Efficacy and Academic Burnout

Variable	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	B	Std. Error	Beta	Contribution percentage	p
Constant	-	-	-	53.414	2.386	-		0.001
Digital Self-Efficacy	.642	.412	.410	0.820	3.25	.203	41.2%	0.001
Academic Burnout	.743	.552	.550	-.964	2.38	.563	55.2%	0.001

The moderate levels of psychological flourishing, digital self-efficacy, and academic burnout among the sample differ from the results of Liu et al. (2023), which showed a higher-than-average level of academic burnout. Academic pressures and challenges in using technology contribute to the research sample's moderate level of digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, and psychological flourishing. Despite having some skills and resources, they do not reach severe burnout or feel highly confident in their digital abilities. The average exposure of the sample to digital technology is not sufficient to foster high levels of digital self-efficacy, but it does prevent very low levels. Support networks from classmates or parents may be limited or inconsistent, impacting psychological flourishing and academic burnout. Students may partially adapt to stress but lack the skills to fully adapt to academic requirements, maintaining an average level of psychological flourishing. Limited resources to develop psychological flourishing, such as extracurricular activities, training courses, or psychological care, also contribute to this. The lack of clarity of goals or motivation also limits digital self-efficacy and leads to average levels of academic burnout. Therefore, we reject the hypothesis that college students exhibit high levels of digital self-efficacy, academic burnout, and psychological flourishing.

performance expectations. Societies with equal academic expectations perceive neither gender as less competent nor in need of support. Additionally, cultural and educational changes in modern societies may contribute to similar burnout responses.

The absence of gender differences in psychological flourishing is partially consistent with the findings of Ryff and Keyes (1995), who found some slight differences between males and females, with women tending to achieve higher levels in some dimensions related to positive relationships and personal growth, while no significant differences appeared in other dimensions. Similar opportunities, social pressures, and coping strategies can account for the lack of differences in psychological flourishing between males and females. Modern societies offer equal access to education, work, and social support, promoting independence and self-actualization. Both genders use similar strategies to cope with life challenges. Changes in societal roles and increased awareness of mental health have also contributed to equal opportunities for psychological satisfaction and growth.

The absence of gender differences in digital self-efficacy contrasts with Yu and Hu's (2022) findings, which suggest that girls exhibit lower efficacy in specialized digital skills, despite demonstrating superior proficiency in certain tasks compared to boys. Cultural and social changes, such as women's increased participation in digital education and the technological labor market, explain the lack of gender-based differences in digital self-efficacy, thereby reducing traditional gender gaps in digital skills. Comprehensive educational curricula, which provide equal digital skills for both genders, can also contribute to this, potentially creating parity in the acquisition of digital confidence. In addition to digital empowerment, there is an increasing focus on training and developing women's digital skills through training programs, which help narrow the gap. There is also a tendency to view differences in digital self-

The differences according to year of study in digital self-efficacy are in favor of fourth-year students. Although digital self-efficacy is a relatively new variable, Zhao et al. (2021) and Pumptow and Brahm (2021) found significant differences in students' perceptions of their digital skills based on the year of study. They found that students in the upper years tend to have more positive perceptions of their digital competence compared to those in the early years of study. Students in the upper years have gained additional experience and skills in using digital tools more effectively, while students in the early years still face significant challenges in adopting these technologies or may feel incompetent in their use, which in turn influences their perceptions.

The differences according to year of study in academic burnout in favor of second-year students differ from those of Liu et al. (2023), who showed that upper-grade students had higher levels of academic burnout than lower-grade students. Younger

students may experience higher academic pressures and expectations, which can lead to increased stress and academic burnout. They may lack organizational and time management skills compared to older students who have acquired these skills over time. This lack of organization can lead to increased anxiety and stress, contributing to academic burnout. In addition, older students may have better stress management skills and prior academic experiences, making younger students more vulnerable to academic burnout.

The differences according to year of study in psychological flourishing are in favor of fourth-year students. Factors such as self-confidence, stress management, social support, and positive expectations held by high achievers explain the existence of psychological flourishing differences in their favor. High achievers also have a greater sense of self-efficacy, which enhances their psychological flourishing. They also have better strategies for managing stress, such as time management and problem solving. In addition, positive expectations foster the future among high achievers and promote psychological satisfaction and flourishing.

The fact that digital self-efficacy changes depending on achievement level, with higher achievers doing better, is in line with the findings of the Jaya and Sucipto (2023) study, which showed that students who do well in school tend to use technology better, which helps them do better in hybrid learning environments. Also, the study by Pan (2020) detected that students with higher levels of technological self-efficacy displayed a more positive attitude toward self-directed learning. Academic burnout varies based on achievement level, favoring low achievers. Low-achieving students may experience increased psychological stress due to difficulty meeting academic requirements or fear of failure, explaining the differences in academic burnout between high- and low-achieving students. On the other hand, high-achieving students may possess effective time management and study strategies, while low-achieving students may lack these skills.

The psychological flourishing of high achievers varies depending on their achievement level. High achievers' self-confidence, stress management, social support, and positive expectations explain the presence of psychological flourishing in their favor. High achievers also have a greater sense of self-efficacy, which enhances their psychological flourishing. They also have better strategies for managing stress, such as time management and problem solving. Social support from teachers, family, and peers provides a sense of belonging, and positive expectations about the future promote psychological satisfaction and flourishing.

Digital self-efficacy in science and humanities disciplines is less significant due to the common effects of educational curricula, such as online research and data analysis software, and the integration of digital skills into all academic disciplines. Personal diversity also plays a role, as students with strong digital interests can develop these skills regardless of their field of study, making students more equal in this aspect (Gilbert, 2019; Lamanauskas, 2011; Siddiq & Scherer, 2016).

The absence of differences according to specialization in academic burnout implies that personal factors, coping mechanisms, and the learning environment have a greater influence on burnout levels than the type of major (Tran et al., 2023). Common factors that influence burnout levels regardless of major type may explain the lack of differences in academic burnout among students based on major. Some of these factors include general study pressures, social expectations, and the similar intensity and quantity of academic tasks across different majors. Additionally, students in all majors may have similar strategies for managing stress and coping academically, which limits differences in burnout levels across different majors.

The absence of differences according to specialization in psychological flourishing differs from those of Barbayannis et al. (2022), who indicated that students in academic disciplines related to science and technology face unique challenges, such as high academic pressure, which may affect their psychological flourishing. On the other hand, Moreira-Choez et al. (2024) indicated that literary disciplines may provide a more supportive environment on an emotional level, which enhances their psychological flourishing. Common supportive factors, regardless of the nature of the major, may explain the lack of differences in psychological flourishing among students based on major. These include a supportive academic environment, positive social relationships within the college, and the personal coping strategies that students use. It also reflects the ability of students to develop a sense of accomplishment and flourishing regardless of major, as everyone may find different sources of motivation, belonging, and support, leading to similar levels of psychological flourishing across different specializations.

The level of digital self-efficacy explains the predictability of psychological flourishing, as individuals with high digital self-efficacy frequently experience higher levels of psychological flourishing. This is due to self-confidence and an enhanced sense of competence, as individuals with digital self-efficacy feel more confident in their ability to interact with technology and accomplish related tasks. This confidence enhances their sense of personal competence, which is positively related to psychological flourishing, as they feel able to control their academic or work environment and face challenges.

The ability to manage stress and resilience can also explain it, as individuals with high digital self-efficacy tend to be less susceptible to psychological pressures that arise from using technology or adapting to digital challenges. This reduces their stress levels, which contributes to their sense of psychological comfort and thus to achieving higher levels of psychological flourishing.

Digital self-efficacy also helps individuals integrate into the digital environment efficiently and effectively, which increases their sense of engagement and positivity. This positive adaptation enhances their sense of belonging to their educational or professional environment, which is an important component of achieving psychological flourishing. In addition, digital self-efficacy motivates individuals to engage in new activities, whether for learning, entertainment, or personal

development. They feel they have a goal and a desire to achieve it, which enhances their desire for personal growth and continuous learning and leads to psychological flourishing. Finally, digital self-efficacy provides individuals with a sense of independence and self-reliance in solving technology-related problems. This sense of independence is considered one of the essential elements of psychological flourishing, as it contributes to enhancing the sense of control and the ability to make decisions independently.

Digital self-efficacy predicts psychological flourishing by enabling individuals to effectively use digital tools, interact with the digital world, and have confidence in their abilities to manage digital challenges (Ulfert-Blank & Schmidt, 2022). High digital self-efficacy leads to higher psychological well-being, as it enhances self-confidence, allows for adaptability to technology, supports healthy social relationships through digital communication, and allows individuals to achieve personal and professional goals. This sense of control and balance in digital lives positively impacts psychological health, reducing stress and promoting psychological well-being.

Also, the predictability of psychological flourishing through the level of academic burnout can be explained by the fact that academic burnout is a significant indicator of an individual's psychological state in their academic environment, affecting their psychological health. High levels of burnout lead to negative feelings like frustration and loss of enthusiasm, reducing psychological satisfaction and happiness.

Additionally, academic burnout can lead to social isolation, stress, and a decline in psychological flourishing. It can cause individuals to withdraw from social interactions, draining resources and reducing their motivation for personal growth. This lack of motivation, while associated with psychological flourishing, limits the achievement of this vital aspect of life.

Conclusion

This study explores the important relationships between psychological flourishing, digital self-efficacy, and academic burnout among university students. The findings reveal several key insights into the connections between these variables. Firstly, a significant positive correlation was found between digital self-efficacy and psychological flourishing, while a negative correlation was observed between digital self-efficacy and academic burnout. Additionally, academic burnout was negatively correlated with psychological flourishing.

When comparing the variables across different student groups, no significant differences were found based on gender or specialization. However, significant differences were observed in relation to year of study and academic achievement. For instance, fourth-year students demonstrated higher levels of psychological flourishing and digital self-efficacy than second-year students. Furthermore, high achievers showed greater levels of digital self-efficacy and psychological flourishing, while experiencing lower levels of academic burnout compared to low achievers.

This study is important as it contributes to understanding the relationship between psychological and technological factors affecting students' academic experience, helping in the development of strategies to improve psychological well-being and reduce academic burnout.

Recommendations

Universities should take the following actions:

Enhancing students' digital self-efficacy through targeted training programs can improve academic performance, reduce academic burnout, and support long-term psychological well-being. To achieve this, universities should collaborate with technology experts to offer practical workshops on educational software, e-learning platforms, and online collaboration tools, while policymakers provide incentives for developing specialized technological programs. Training initiatives should focus on strengthening students' digital skills and confidence in using technology for learning, supported by curricular revisions that formally integrate digital competencies. Interactive online training sessions can further familiarize students with e-learning tools and offer guidance on time management and effective technology use, accompanied by the necessary technical support ensured by policymakers. In addition, providing psychological support sessions—either online or on campus—can help students manage technology-related stress, while workshops on stress management techniques such as breathing exercises and meditation can offer further coping strategies for academic burnout, contingent upon policymakers' logistical and financial backing. Awareness activities emphasizing balance between personal life and academic responsibilities, as well as opportunities for non-academic pursuits like sports, arts, and social participation, can enhance students' mental health, supported through institutional budgets or educational grants. Finally, fostering social collaboration through study groups, student clubs, and online communities can strengthen students' sense of belonging and engagement, provided that policymakers allocate the necessary resources and infrastructure to sustain these initiatives. Organize social and cultural events between students and faculty members to build a healthy academic environment that promotes psychological support and well-being. Policymakers should support these events by providing funding and guidance to ensure effective organization.

Limitations

While this study provides valuable insights, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the research relied on self-reported measures, which may introduce response bias and limit the objectivity of the findings. Second, the cross-sectional design restricts the ability to infer causal relationships between psychological flourishing, digital self-efficacy, and academic burnout. Third, the study was conducted with a sample of 550 students from Kafrelsheikh University, which may limit the generalizability of the results to students in other universities or cultural contexts. Finally, the study did not account for other potential factors, such as personality traits or environmental influences, which might also impact the observed relationships.

Future research could address these limitations by employing longitudinal designs, incorporating more diverse samples, and exploring additional variables.

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